

THERMODYNAMICALLY CONSISTENT JOHNSON-COOK-LIKE MATERIAL MODEL IN COSSERAT MEDIA UNDER LARGE DEFORMATIONS FOR FUTURE MANUFACTURING SIMULATION

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Summary Simulations of manufacturing techniques involving metals deserve proper attention when material softening occurs. It is, in fact, well known that the classical set of equations governing the equilibrium yields to non-unique solutions when the material experiences softening. In this article we make use of the Cosserat theory as a possible solution to this problem. We present a Cosserat theory under a large deformation framework, enriched with a thermodynamically-consistent Johnson-Cook-like description of the material behavior. The theory has been used to simulate localization phenomena in a Hat-Shaped Specimen test.

MOTIVATIONS

Most metal transformation processes, such as machining, friction stir welding and superplastic forming, induce large deformations and high deformation rates in the material. In some cases, at high strain rate, and for specific metals, the deformation localizes into adiabatic shear bands, i.e. zones in which the material exothermically deforms, mostly by shear. At this location, the heat production rate due to plastic deformation may result larger than the heat diffusion rate, thus inducing the material to locally retain high temperature and to subsequently experience thermal softening.

Under these circumstances, the classical models used in Continuum Mechanics result to be inadequate to predict the deformation of the media and material behavior, and the causes lie in the loss of hyperbolicity of the *Partial Differential Equations* (PDE) governing the equilibrium [De Borst and Mühlhaus 1992]. This inadequacy appears as mesh dependency if these PDEs were to be discretized through *Finite Element Methods* (FEMs). The set of PDEs therefore requires a regularization method. One possible solution involves the introduction of non-local quantities at the constitutive law level (gradient-enhanced models). Among many other possible candidates, in the current work we decided to employ a Cosserat description of the media to solve the problem.

The Cosserat description of the media is a generalization of the classical continuum mechanical model, in the specific, the Cosserat brothers [E. Cosserat and F. Cosserat 1909] provided a model in which the microstructural rotation is decoupled from the material rotation. In the classical models instead, by adopting the point of view of the Cosserats, the microstructure rotation follows inertially the material rotation.

Within our scopes, the Cosserat model would allow us to enlarge the domain in which the ellipticity of the PDEs is retained, thus avoiding problems related to non-uniqueness of the solution and mesh dependency when metal manufacturing processes ought to be simulated. This is achieved through the adoption of the gradient of the microrotation as an additional deformation measure, consequently introducing a characteristic length in the model.

Another fundamental feature introduced by the adoption of the Cosserat model is that we are able to characterize the material response with more sophisticated models. The microstructural rotation and its gradient are used as additional deformation measures, thus contributing in defining the constitutive behavior of the material.

MODEL DESCRIPTION

The hyper-elastic version of the Cosserat model can be initially described by explicitly stating the definition of the internal power $p^{(i)}$ as:

$$p^{(i)} = \boldsymbol{\sigma} : (\mathbf{v} \otimes \nabla - \boldsymbol{\omega}) + \mathbf{m} : \left(\overset{\times}{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \otimes \nabla \right); \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the non-symmetric stress tensor, $(\mathbf{v} \otimes \nabla - \boldsymbol{\omega})$ is the Cosserat strain rate, $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ is the skew-symmetric matrix created from the pseudo-vector of the microstructure rotation velocity, \mathbf{m} is the couple stress tensor and $\left(\overset{\times}{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \otimes \nabla \right)$ is the Cosserat wryness rate.

The Cosserat deformations, indicated with a sharp sign, can be written according to the Lagrangian description as:

$$\sharp \mathbf{F} = \mathbf{R}^T \cdot \mathbf{F}; \quad (2)$$

$$\sharp \mathbf{\Gamma} = \mathbf{R}^T \cdot \mathbf{\Gamma}; \quad (3)$$

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Figure 1: Equivalent plastic strain distribution at the localization band during Hat-Shaped specimen test under compression (a) and flow stress distribution along the cross section passing through the shear band (b).

where \mathbf{F} is the deformation gradient, \mathbf{R} is the rotation matrix describing the microstructure rotation and $\mathbf{\Gamma}$ is the Cosserat wryness. To provide a robust material characterization, the constitutive response of the hyper-elastic model is derived from the Helmholtz free energy, which we defined as:

$$\rho\psi\left(\#_{\mathbf{F}}, \#_{\mathbf{\Gamma}}\right) = \frac{\lambda}{2} (J - 1)^2 + \mu \|\text{sym}\left(\#_{\mathbf{F}}\right) - \mathbf{I}\|^2 + \mu_c \|\text{skew}\left(\#_{\mathbf{F}} - \mathbf{I}\right)\|^2 + \frac{\beta}{2} \|\#_{\mathbf{\Gamma}}\|^2; \quad (4)$$

Work has already been done on a thermodynamically-consistent visco-plastic material model in the small deformation framework. A Johnson-Cook-like model has been implemented in the Cosserat theory where the thermal variation is evaluated through a robust thermodynamic approach. The Taylor-Quinney coefficient, built on assumptions that are not valid anymore for our applications, has been replaced with an explicit evaluation of the contribution of the plastic work to the thermal variation:

$$\dot{T} = \frac{\left(\boldsymbol{\sigma} : \dot{\mathbf{e}}^p + \boldsymbol{\mu} : \dot{\mathbf{k}}^p - \frac{\partial\psi_\alpha}{\partial p} \dot{p}\right)}{\rho \left[C_\varepsilon + \frac{\partial C_\varepsilon}{\partial T} (T - T_0)\right]}; \quad (5)$$

The Equations of the hyper-elastic model above have been first simplified such that only one rotation is allowed (bi-dimensional rotation) while keeping a full three dimensional displacement field, and then they have been discretized such as to be implemented in a Finite Element solver. Finally, the thermodynamically-consistent Johnson-Cook-like model has been implemented in the theory.

RESULTS

By simulating the compression of a Hat-Shaped Specimen [Peirs et al. 2010], it has been shown that the Cosserat theory is a possible solution to the mesh dependency problem (Figure 1a), but, more importantly, it has also been shown that the theory can simultaneously predict material viscous hardening and thermal softening (Figure 1b).

The results of the on-going work will be presented at the ICTAM in August. In particular, a similar thermodynamically consistent visco-plastic model will be implemented in the large deformation framework, and it will be subsequently calibrated through the Hat-Shaped specimen test, in which it will also be possible to identify the effect of the characteristic length of the model.

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